

Additional faunistic records of Hemiptera and their collected altitudes in the Eastern and Southeastern Anatolia

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ABSTRACT: Three species of family Lygaeidae, *Melanocoryphus tristrami* (Douglas & Scott, 1868), *Melanocoryphus albomaculatus* (Goeze, 1778), *Ischnocoris punctulatus* Fieber, 1861, one species of family Rhopalidae, *Corizus fenestella fenestella* Horvath, 1917, one species of family Rhyparochromidae, *Aellopus atratus* (Goeze, 1778) and *Aelia virgata* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1841) (Pentatomidae) are listed. All of species were newly faunistic record of collecting areas. The altitudes of the species varied between 110 meters and 1400 meters.

KEYWORDS: Fauna, East and Southeast Anatolia, new faunistic record.

To cite this article: Özgen, İ., Paride, D., 2022, Additional faunistic records of Hemiptera and their collected altitudes in the Eastern and Southeastern Anatolia, *J.Het.Turk.*, 4(1):58-61

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.6590310

To link to this article: <https://www.j-het.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/V41-A8.pdf>

Received: May 10, 2022; **Revised:** May 24, 2022; **Accepted:** May 25, 2022; **Published online:** May 30, 2022

INTRODUCTION

The latest faunistic paper with Heteroptera Latreille, 1810 fauna of Eastern and southeastern Anatolia region were recorded by some recent papers (Péricart, 1998 a,b; Önder et al., 2006; Bolu et al., 2006; Dursun et al., 2010; Dursun, 2011, 2012; Dursun & Fent, 2013; Yıldırım et al., 2013; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Çerçi et al., 2018; Dioli & Özgen, 2019; Özgen & Dioli,

2019; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Özgen et al., 2021). In this study; The faunistic records of these species are given along with their altitudes.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The specimens were collected by a net and aspirated. Collected specimens were examined in the laboratory by using an Olympus SZX 7 stereomicroscope and identified by second author.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In totaly, The faunistic records of six species were given:

Lygaeidae Schilling, 1829***Melanocoryphus tristrami* (Douglas & Scott, 1868)**

Material examined: Elazığ, Baskil, Şahaplı, 30.05.2018, 3 exc.

Distribution in Palearctic region: (Péricart, 2001).

Distribution in Turkey: Adana, Ankara, Bursa, Hatay, Kastamonu, Konya, Mersin, Niğde, Sakarya (Önder et al., 2006)

Note: First record in East Anatolia.

Altitude of collected: 1130 meter.

***Melanocoryphus albomaculatus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Material examined: Tunceli, Karşılar village, 16.05.2019, 2 exc.

Distribution in Palearctic region: (Péricart, 2001).

Distribution in Turkey: Ankara, Çankırı, Erzincan, Erzurum, Malatya (Küçükbasmacı, and Kıyak, 2015; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Özgen et al., 2021).

Note: First record in Tunceli province.

Altitude of collected: 1110 meter.

***Ischnocoris punctulatus* Fieber, 1861**

Material examined: Tunceli, Karşılar village, 16.05.2019, 3 exc.

Distribution in Turkey: Ankara, Edirne (Péricart, 1998a; Yence, 2019).

Note: It is found that between 1500 to 2000 meter in Aladağlar “Kazıklı Ali Kanyonu” “1600 meter” (Yence, 2019).

It was first record in East Anatolia.

Altitude of collected: 1110 meter.

Rhopalidae Amyot & Serville, 1843***Corizus fenestella fenestella* Horvath, 1917**

Material examined: Elazığ, Maden, 01.06.2022, 11exc.

Distribution in Turkey: Diyarbakır (Önder et al., 2006; Bolu, 2020; Özgen et al., 2021).

Note: First record in Elazığ province.

Altitude of collected: 1090 meter.

Rhyparochromidae Amyot & Serville, 1843***Aellopus atratus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Material examined: Bingöl, Solhan, 15.06.2022, 2 exc.

Distribution in Turkey: Elazığ, Isparta (Fent and Japoshvili, 2012; Özgen).

Altitude of collected: 1400 meter.

Pentatomidae Leach, 1815***Aelia virgata* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1841)**

Material examined: Elazığ, Günbağı village, 22.05.2018, 2 exc.

Distribution in Turkey: Afyon, Amasya, Ankara, Bilecik, Edirne, Gaziantep, Iğdır, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kırklareli, Uşak (Lodos et al., 1998; Fent & Aktaş, 1999; Dursun & Kartal, 2008; Çerçi and Gözüaçık, 2019).

Altitude of collected: 1390 meter.

The species obtained in the study were detected for the first time in their location. The altitudes of the species varied between 110 meters and 1400 meters. These records contribute to the Heteroptera fauna of the regions.

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